

D 2.4 – Simulation results report

HighScape - High efficiency, high power density, cost effective, scalable and modular power electronics and control solutions for electric vehicles

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ELAPHE	Elaphe Pogonske Tehnologije DOO
TENNECO	Tenneco Automotive Europe BVBA
AVL DE	AVL Deutschland GmbH
AUDI	AUDI Aktiengesellschaft
TOFAS	TOFAS TURK OTOMOBIL FABRIKASI ANONIM SIRKETI
USR	University of Surrey
AIG	Armengaud Innovate GmbH

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Long Version
AWD	All Wheel Drive
BEV	Battery Electric Vehicle
DC/DC	Direct Current to Direct Current
FTP	Federal Test Procedure
IWM	In-Wheel Motor
LUT	Look-Up Table
NMPC	Nonlinear Model Predictive Control
n-D	n-Dimensional
PE	Power electronics
RWD	Rear wheel drive
R&D	Research and development
VSM	Virtual Vehicle System
WBG	Wide Band Gap (semiconductor)
WLTC	Worldwide Harmonized Light Vehicles Test Cycle
WP	Work package

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1 Executive Summary

1.1 Overview of project

Focused on BEV architectures with distributed multiple wheel drives, and, specifically, in-wheel powertrains, HighScape will explore the feasibility of a family of highly efficient power electronics components and systems, and including integrated traction inverters, onboard chargers, DC/DC converters, and electric drives for auxiliaries and actuators. The proposed solutions will be assessed on test rigs and on two differently sized BEV prototypes.

The project will result in:

- i. component integration with the incorporation of the WBG traction inverters within the in-wheel machines to achieve zero footprint of the electric powertrain on the sprung mass; the functional integration of the traction inverter with the on-board charger, and the incorporation of the latter and the DC/DC converters within the battery pack; and the implementation of multi-motor and fault-tolerant inverter solutions for the auxiliaries and chassis actuators;
- ii. novel solutions, including the implementation of reconfigurable winding topologies of the drive, as well as integrated and predictive thermal management at the vehicle level, with the adoption of phase changing materials within the power electronic components;
- iii. the achievement and demonstration of significantly higher levels of power density, specific power and energy efficiency for the resulting power electronic systems and related drives;
- iv. major cost reductions thanks to the dual use of parts, subsystem modularity, and model-based design to eliminate overengineering; and
- v. increased dependability and reliability of the power electronics systems, enabled by design and intelligent predictive health monitoring algorithms.

Through HighScape, the participants will establish new knowledge and industrial leadership in key digital technologies, and, therefore, directly contribute to Europe's Key Strategic Orientations as well as actively support the transformation towards zero tailpipe emission road mobility (2Zero).

1.2 Deliverable Objective and Results

Deliverable D2.4 aims to validate the role of HighScape Power Electronic (PE) solutions in enhancing Battery Electric Vehicle (BEV) performance across diverse operational scenarios. By utilizing a simulation-based framework developed collaboratively by USR and project partners, it provides actionable insights to refine HighScape solutions and align them with advancing technologies.

The simulation activities, particularly the thermal dynamics studies detailed in Section 4, successfully emulated the power loss and temperature profiles of the power electronic components when integrated into the vehicle. These insights were instrumental in the early-stage development of the vehicle thermal management system under WP5. The use of the simulation toolchain, especially in scenarios with limited access to physical components or bench test data, shows its effectiveness in addressing critical development needs.

2 Introduction

The Horizon Europe HighScape project aims to develop highly efficient power electronic components and systems for BEVs, including integrated traction inverters, onboard chargers, DC/DC converters, and electric drives. In this project the Work Package 2 (WP2) establishes the project's foundational stage, where technical requirements for a BEV system are conceptualized. These requirements are validated through simulation in the simulation toolchain developed in WP2 as well. The outputs from WP2 support the R&D activities in WP3,4,5,6 and inform the BEV test plan in WP7. This work package is led by USR and is divided into four tasks, each resulting in a deliverable: D2.1, D2.2, D2.3, and D2.4.

Figure 1 The MATLAB/VSM co-simulation schematics.

Figure 1 shows the schematic of the co-simulation platform developed and submitted in D2.3. The operating mechanism of the simulation toolchain is such that the vehicle controls will be implemented in Simulink, and the vehicle response to controls is calculated in VSM. Using the technical requirements laid out in D2.1 and D2.2 the HighScape simulation toolchain incorporates all the surrogate models generated within the project. Preliminary simulations were carried out, and the simulation results were reported in the D2.3 to demonstration of the feasibility of the simulator.

In D2.4 the focus is on validating the simulation models developed in Task 2.3 and parametrized according to the technical and application-specific requirements outlined in Tasks 2.1 and 2.2. The deliverable aims to deliver actionable insights into the HighScape solution's effectiveness in optimizing BEV performance, focusing on its adaptability to real-world challenges. The scope of this validation spans a wide range of operational and ambient conditions critical to BEV efficiency and reliability. It includes assessments under extreme thermal variations, defrosting needs, and demanding driving cycles to simulate real-world scenarios that BEVs may encounter.

Simulation based validation work is dependent on the surrogate models provided by the HighScape's component and system suppliers, which includes AVL, BLW, ELAPHE, TOFAS, UGent, POLITO, and TENNECO. These surrogate models are experimental validated data of their component or simulation data from a high-fidelity simulation data of their validated model. In Section 2 of this deliverable the surrogate models of the project partners are presented.

The benefit of the simulation toolchain is that in technical projects with multiple parties working on different technological developments, it can be challenging to consolidate all information and progress into a cohesive framework. A simulation environment helps to integrate these pieces, enabling informed

decision-making across all WPs, even when specific components or integrated systems are not yet available. The thermal dynamic simulation activity reported in the Section 4 of this deliverable is an example of simulation work which helped WP5 in the early-stage work development of their vehicle thermal management system simulation. Simulation toolchain comes in handy and beneficial for such situation i.e. unavailability of components to car.

Another benefit point of simulation toolchain is that the results generated, can be updated swiftly to reflect any ongoing advancements made by HighScape’s component as it is a normal practice that supplier re-parametrizes models to incorporate new technical improvements, allowing for an iterative refinement of the solution. Different case studies and scenarios can be simulated which sometimes is not possible to it on hardware level.

3 Component Surrogate Models and their Integration to Simulation Toolchain

In the high-fidelity vehicle dynamics simulator AVL VSM™ 2023, the Fiat e-Doblo vehicle (developed by TOFAS) is integrated and used for simulations. This vehicle is equipped with two in-wheel motors (IWMs) located on its rear axle. The IWM motor surrogate model is provided by ELAPHE, the traction inverter surrogate model by BLW, and the suspension actuator surrogate model by TENNECO. The following subsections present these surrogate models and detail their integration process into the simulation toolchain.

3.1 IWM Power Loss Maps by ELAPHE

The surrogate model of the IWM motor by ELAPHE is a power loss map which is basically a graphical representation that illustrates how power losses are distributed across different operating conditions of the motor, plotted against speed and torque. These maps complement efficiency maps by showing where and how energy is lost in the motor.

Figure 2 Power loss maps by ELAPHE (a) 2-D view (b) 3-D view

The map (see Figure 2) reveals that power losses are minimal in most of the operating range, as indicated by the dominance of blue regions. However, losses increase significantly at the extremes of torque, particularly at high positive and negative torques, and low speeds, as represented by the red bands at the

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edges. These regions highlight areas of inefficiency that may require attention during motor design or optimization to improve overall performance.

From the 3-D view of Figure 2 (b) it is seen that the minimum power loss value is close zero or very low value in the low speed and loss torque region. This power loss indicates an efficient mode operation of the motor. The power maps shown in Figure 2 are cumulative losses of various power loss, including copper losses caused by resistive effects in the windings due to current flow, iron losses arising from core effects such as hysteresis and eddy currents, and mechanical losses like friction and windage from bearings, seals, and air drag. Additionally, proximity losses, which result from the proximity effect in electrical conductors, and other miscellaneous losses, such as stray load losses or those caused by harmonics and leakage, can be visualized to provide a comprehensive understanding of power dissipation under different operating conditions. Copper loss constitutes the largest portion of the total power loss. The remaining losses are relatively small, with values below 500W. The surrogate model (power loss maps) of the ELAPHE motor is then integrated to the MATLAB/Simulink environment. Figure 3 shows surrogate models added in the power train of BEV in the simulation environment.

Figure 3 Simulation subsystem containing the various surrogate models added in the power train of BEV in the AVL_VSM/Simulink/MATLAB environment.

The benefit of the Simulation toolchain is that at any given point new components can be added as and when the surrogate models are available. Different subsystems are created to categorize different parts (actuators, vehicle control, power electronics and thermal model etc.) of the vehicle as shown in the Figure 3. The Power Electronics subsystem represents the powertrain of the BEV. Figure 4 shows the addition of the motor power losses into the 2-D look-up table (LUT) of Simulink block. Here magnet loss, iron loss and mechanical losses are summed together as other losses. These are the losses which are independent or least affected by the motor current and temperature variation.

Figure 4 Implementation of the motor surrogate model using Simulink LUT blocks.

As shown in Figure 4, the copper loss and proximity effect have provisions for scaling based on variations in motor temperature. These scaling factors are provided by the component provider. Similarly, in the future, these can also be scaled based on motor current if further analysis is required. The simulation study offers the flexibility to incorporate temperature and current scaling as needed, providing adaptability for future investigations.

3.2 Inverter Efficiency Maps by BLW

In the power train of the BEV the next surrogate model included is the three phase inverter efficiency maps by BLW. The provided 3D efficiency map is shown in Figure 5. The maps illustrate the performance of an inverter at different temperatures of 175°C, 100°C, 40°C, 20°C, 0°C and -25°C. The map demonstrates a characteristic dip in efficiency in the mid-range of the power-speed domain, where efficiency levels drop below 90%, represented by the lower region in the plot. At lower and higher power or speed ranges, the efficiency improves significantly, reaching values above 95%, as indicated by the yellow regions near the top of the efficiency scale.

The power input on the X-axis is the DC input power to the inverter’s DC bus terminals. From the inverter efficiency plots in Figure 5 it is seen that at the operating temperatures 0°C and 20°C, the efficiency is higher across all speed and power operating points as compared to the higher operating temperatures 175°C and 100°C, which indicates an efficiency drop with the rise of the operating temperature.

Figure 5 Inverter efficiency map by BLW at different temperatures

The Figure 6 shows the integration of the inverter surrogate model into the n-D LUT of Simulink block. Additional input of switching frequency is provided for future analysis. The current form of surrogate model only uses the temperature, power and vehicle speed as its inputs. For studies where the traction input power to the motor (i.e. the output power of the inverter) is available then the inverter output power efficiency can be used instead. With the input power and efficiency data provided available the output power can be derived. The reshaping of the efficiency maps is done prior to the simulation to get the efficiency maps based on output power. Figure 6 shows the transformed surrogate model which is the efficiency map with output power on its Y-axis integrated to the power electronic subsystem of Figure 3. The input power efficiency surrogate model can be utilized when the DC input power information is available in the simulation case study work.

Figure 6 Implementation of the inverter surrogate model using Simulink LUT blocks.

Needless to say, if the efficiency and the input/output power data is available one can either choose to generate the power loss maps prior to simulation and have a power loss LUT as the surrogate model instead of the efficiency maps surrogate model or get it calculated on the fly during the simulation as shown in the Figure 6.

3.3 Chassis Actuator (Active Suspension) by TENNECO

The active suspension surrogate model is provided by TENNECO. It uses sensors, actuators, and control algorithms to generate forces that counteract vehicle roll. The full suspension system consists of damper actuator, hydraulic circuit and pump unit. This is illustrated in Figure 7. The inputs to the model are the desired damping forces, suspension displacement and desired roll moment, the outputs are the actual force and actual roll moment.

The active suspension surrogate model is then integrated into the co-simulation platform that combines the high-fidelity vehicle dynamics simulator. Using this validated surrogate model of TENNECO’s active suspension actuator a simulation work was carried out.

Figure 7 TENNECO suspension full simulation model

Figure 8 shows the MATLAB/Simulink function block of TENNECO’s surrogate model. The model takes various inputs, including roll moment request (in Nm), left and right suspension displacements and velocities (in m and m/s), and damping force requests (in N) for the left and right suspension systems. Based on these inputs, the model outputs the forces acting on the left and right sides (in N) as well as the roll moment (in Nm). There are two such models, one for the front and one for the rear axle.

Active roll moment control and active damping force control are independent though there are both actuated by the damper. Here the active roll moment control resulted force and the active damping force together form the damper force as the output. The total roll moment is the combined action of damper force and passive spring force. There is no anti-roll bar which is replaced by this damper supporting active roll moment control.

Figure 8 MATLAB/Simulink function block of TENNECO’s surrogate model of the active suspension (a) front axle (b) rear axle

Figure 9 shows the surrogate Simulink model of these active dampers. The total damper force at each corner, the sum of the active damping force and the force to generate active roll moment, will be sent to the vehicle model in VSM, while vehicle suspension velocities will be feed backed to the model. Active damping force requests and active roll moment requests are obtained from the high-level controls.

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Figure 9 Active suspension model in Simulink.

At each corner, the damping force is constrained within the outer and inner bounds as shown in Figure 10 (the force is normalised against a value close to the outer bound force at speed 0.5 m/s). These bounds are nonlinear along the suspension velocity. The damping dynamic is simplified as a first-order transfer function between the requested and actual damping force.

On each axle, the active roll moment request is first converted to the active force requests on the left and right corners of the axle, according to the track width. One side provides a pull force while the other side provides a rebound force. The damper's active force dynamics are modelled as a second-order transfer function with different gains to reflect the difference in pull and rebound behaviours. Figure 11 shows the dynamic responses of pull and rebound active damper forces to actuate an active roll moment request.

Figure 10 Active damping force limits.

Figure 11 Response of pull and rebound active forces for active roll moment.

4 Thermal Dynamics Simulation Work

The aim of this simulation activity is to generate the time histories of the power losses and temperatures of the IWM and the inverter for different driving cycles. This power loss data is then utilized by WP5 for the predictions of the vehicle’s thermal management simulations. Since the power loss of the power train component is a function of temperature, thermal dynamics models for motor and inverter were developed. These thermal dynamics models were then integrated into the simulation toolchain as shown in Figure 3. The power losses from the surrogate models of motor (power loss maps) and inverter

(efficiency maps) provided by ELAPHE and BLW respectively are the input to the thermal dynamics surrogate model.

4.1 Methodology

The Figure 12 shows the block diagram of the system level integration of the thermal dynamic surrogate model into the simulation toolchain. The simulation runs in combination with the AVL-VSM/Simulink simulation toolchain. The vehicle dynamics are handled by the VSM software, and the component level dynamics and vehicle controls are implemented in Simulink, and the vehicle response to controls is calculated in VSM.

Figure 12 Schematic representation of the overall functioning of the proposed methodology.

The vehicle parameters used are that of Fiat E-Doblo. The high-fidelity simulation is then made to run on the different driving cycles e.g. WLTC and a speed profile driving up the Großglockner pass (Austria). The higher-level vehicle controller manoeuvres the vehicle to follow the speed reference of the drive cycle. As for battery powered vehicles, the motor torque demand is supplied from the traction inverter. The power loss of the motor and the inverter are then fed into the thermal dynamics model.

4.1.1 Thermal Dynamics Model and integration

The thermal dynamics surrogate model of the electric machine and the inverter has been considered with a basic formulation represented by the following first order differential equation, where C_{eq} represents the equivalent thermal capacity of the electric motor and K_{heat} is the heat transfer coefficient of the electric motor. T_{amb} is ambient temperature, and T is the component temperature.

$$\frac{dT}{dt} = \frac{1}{C_{eq}} (P_{loss} - K_{heat}(T - T_{amb})) \quad (1)$$

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A MATLAB function is used in Simulink to model the thermal dynamics eq. (1) as shown in Figure 13. The output of the thermal dynamics model is the temperature, which is then fed back into the temperature-dependent motor and inverter models. The power loss of the inverter model is computed using the input power, output power and efficiency information. These models, in turn, provide updated power loss values.

Figure 13 Block diagram showing the thermal dynamics model arrangement in Simulink using MATLAB Function.

The power loss splitting function shown in Figure 13 is to decide the proportion of the power loss on the component. For the preliminary support work, the weight components are considered 100%. This provision is provided for future study work to be able to analyse the mutual interference of heat loss due to the motor and inverter if needed.

Figure 14 depicts the implementation of the power loss splitting function and thermal dynamic model internal block of thermal dynamic model in the Simulink toolchain.

Figure 14 Screenshot of Simulink showing thermal dynamic model internal block of thermal dynamic model in the Simulink toolchain.

As seen in the Figure 14 provision is made to study both 2IWM and 4IWM drive system. While the HighScape project focuses on 2IWM, the 4IWM drive study is included for exploratory purposes to assess the impact of temperature variations in both configurations. As the simulation progresses, the temperature of each component changes over time as a function of the power loss and time.

4.1.2 Simulation Use Cases

The simulation was carried out for three different driving environments, these environments are requested by the project partners to facilitate their vehicle thermal management system in WP5.

Case 1: WLTC drive cycle

Case 2: Großglockner drive cycle showing the uphill case

Case 3: Heat up test for vehicle cabin

The WLTC drive cycle was simulated for different ambient temperatures starting at -10°C, 0°C, 15°C, 20°C, 30°C and 40°C respectively. The Großglockner drive cycle was carried out at ambient temperatures starting at 30°C. The heat up test for the vehicle cabin started at a temperature at -20°C, the measurement duration was 30min, the vehicle speed was 50 km/h.

4.2 Tuning of the Coefficients C_{eq} and K_{heat} of the Thermal Dynamics Model

The value of C_{eq} and K_{heat} of the motor winding thermal dynamics model of eq. (1) is done empirically using the power loss maps and winding temperature information for certain torque and speed provided by ELAPHE for their base model as given in Table 1

Table 1 Winding Temperature for certain speed and torque for one transient working point by ELAPHE

WP	Speed [rpms]	Torque [Nm]	T_inlet [°C]	T_winding_max [°C, approx.]
1	600	800	20	100
2	600	800	40	115
3	600	800	60	135
4	545	540	20	55
5	545	540	40	75
6	370	900	20	125
7	370	900	40	145
8	370	900	70	195

Referring to the working points in Table 1, it is noticed, that there is a high dependency between inlet flow rates and max temperatures in a motor. This dependency is not included in this evaluation, but rather the most representative flow rate related working points is added, which is expected to be present in reality.

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The value of C_{eq} and K_{heat} were tuned in MATLAB/Simulink using the motor surrogate model. The constant torque and speed value from Table 1 were given as the input to the motor power-loss LUT. The power loss value is then fed to the simple first-order thermal dynamics model which then calculates the temperature. The generated temperature is fed back to the power loss model as shown in Figure 13 to account for the effects of operating temperature on the copper loss and proximity loss. The coefficients C_{eq} and K_{heat} were empirically adjusted until the temperature of the thermal dynamic model closely matched the motor winding temperature given in Table 1. The temperature dynamics model uses the motor winding power loss, so the tuned temperature is the motor winding temperature.

Figure 15 Simulink results showing the temperature value after tuning C_{eq} and K_{heat} value at T_{amb} of 20°C, at of motor torque and speed combination of 800 Nm and 600 rpm respectively.

Figure 15 shows the Simulink results, here the blue waveform is the reference temperature value for 800 Nm, 600 rpm and T_{amb} of 20°C, and the orange waveform shows the temperature value after tuning the C_{eq} and K_{heat} . The heat transfer coefficient and K_{heat} accounts for the effect of the coolant, specifically considering oil cooling. This reflects the temperature data provided by ELAPHE, which includes oil cooling.

Figure 16 Temperature profile of ELAPHE baseline motor on predefined testing conditions.

Further measurement temperature data of baseline motor L1600 on predefined testing conditions as shown in Figure 16 was provided by ELAPHE for the tuning of the thermal model. Here the motor runs the following scenario: Preheating on the continuous torque – FTP cycle– heating up again in the continuous torque – WLTC. At this scenario motor currents, voltages, and temperatures, as well as speed and torque were measured. There are three runs with different coolant temperatures: 20°C, 40°C, 60°C. The rotor housing temperature is measured to estimate the magnet temperature, and the magnet temperature is taken approximately 4°C lower than the rotor housing, and the winding temperature at two different thermistors and the average of these two is taken.

As explained previously here too the tuning process started by empirically trying to find the value of C_{eq} and K_{heat} for the motor winding thermal dynamics model in MATLAB/Simulink such that its temperature match closely to the temperature provided by ELAPHE for the entire test conditions.

Since the first order thermal dynamics model is simple and is unable to match the pre-heated regions (high constant torque value) and the drive cycle regions (low transient torque value) with one C_{eq} and K_{heat} value. Hence a new approach was implemented where three sets of C_{eq} and K_{heat} were blended to create one LUT for C_{eq} and K_{heat} respectively.

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Figure 17 Simulink results showing the measured temperature and simulated temperature of the thermal dynamics model after tuning value of C_{eq} and K_{heat} focusing (a) matching the drive cycle temperature region (b) matching both the regions (c) matching the pre-heated constant temperature region.

The first set of tuning of C_{eq} and K_{heat} is done focusing on matching the thermal dynamics model temperature to the temperature in the drive cycle regions of the test condition where the temperature is seen to be changing as shown in Figure 17 (a) and the third set of tuning is done focusing on matching the tune temperature to preheated region regions where the temperature is seen to be constant as shown in Figure 17 (c). The second set of the tuning value taken between the first and the third set as shown in Figure 17 (b).

Then these three sets of C_{eq} and K_{heat} are scheduled as function of torque demand by means of a look-up table as shown in Figure 18. The breakaway point for the LUT is the torque value. For low torque operating region the C_{eq} and K_{heat} value of Figure 17 (a) is used and for high torque operating region the C_{eq} and K_{heat} values of Figure 17 (c) is used. Based on the torque input the output values of C_{eq} and K_{heat} for the winding is generated from the LUT.

Figure 18 LUT of tuned values of C_{eq} and K_{heat} with input motor torque as breakaway points (a) C_{eq} (b) K_{heat} .

Finally, the Figure 19 shows the Simulink results showing the tuned temperature value and the measured temperature for the testing environment provided by ELAPHE. This result shows that using a blended LUT C_{eq} and K_{heat} enhances the performance of the simple thermal dynamics model to match its temperature to that of the measured value for wide operating range of speed and torque input to the motor.

Figure 19 Simulink results showing the measured temperature from ELAPHE and simulated temperature of the thermal dynamics model after using the LUT of C_{eq} and K_{heat} at T_{amb} of 20°C.

4.2.1 Validation of the Motor Winding Thermal Dynamics Model

The tuning of the C_{eq} and K_{heat} as explained above is done using only the motor surrogate model in Simulink without inclusion of the vehicle model from VSM. Next with the tuned parameters the simulation is run on VSM/Simulink toolchain with inclusion of the vehicle dynamics.

For the validation simulation the goal is to simulate the WLTC with preheated temperature value as shown in Figure 19. The expectation is that the thermal dynamics model with the tuned coefficient value be able to emulate a similar pattern. In the VSM/Simulink toolchain the WLTC is given as the road profile to the vehicle control unit as shown in the Figure 3. In the thermal dynamics model the T_{amb} is the coolant inlet temperature. The initial operating temperature was 95°C.

Figure 20 VSM/Simulink simulation results (a) plots showings tuned motor winding temperature variation for WLTP drive cycle from a preheated condition of 95°C with thermal dynamics model (b) WLTP drive cycle with preheated temperature data by ELAPHE

Figure 20 (a) shows the simulation results of VSM/Simulink with a preheated condition of 95°C with the tuned thermal model parameters i.e. With C_{eq} and K_{heat} generated from the LUT in shown in Figure 18. The

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motor winding temperature is seen to closely depict the similar pattern by ELAPHE as shown in Figure 20 (b). There is a small discrepancy, this could be due to the difference in the vehicle parameters used in our VSM/Simulink and ELAPHE for their testing purposes. Overall, the proposed thermal dynamic model can show a similar pattern as expected.

Table 2 Motor Parameters with tuned values

Parameters	Value
Mass (m)	25.30 kg
Surface area (A)	0.10 m ²
Radius	217.5 mm
Axial length	12.85 cm
C_{eq}	LUT as shown in Figure 18 (a)
K_{heat}	LUT as shown in Figure 18 (b)

Table 2 presents the values used for the simulation work. Here K_{heat} is tuned such that it imposes the cooling effect of the motor winding from the coolant.

4.2.2 Assumption made for Inverter Thermal Dynamics Model

Since the measured temperature data for inverter is not available at this juncture C_{eq} and K_{heat} values for inverter are assumed based on the motor dimension. The motor parameters were provided by ELAPHE (see Table 2). The Inverter dimensions is approximated between 15-20 cm diameter and 3-6 cm depth (liquid-cooled, as motor and inverter will be liquid cooled). The tuning of inverter the C_{eq} and K_{heat} is done such that it remains closely to that of motor winding.

Table 3 Inverter parameter assumed for simulation considering a 3-Phase Inverter.

Parameters	Value
Mass (m)	2.6 kg
Specific heat capacity of Aluminium (c)	900 J/(kgK) (Monero, October 2017)
Surface area (A)	0.022 m ²
Heat transfer coefficient (h)	130 W/(m ² K)
C_{eq}	2340 J/K (i.e. m*c)
K_{heat}	3 W/K (i.e. A*h)

The equivalent thermal capacity is calculated with assumed mass and material (Shahjalal, et al., January 2023). The K_{heat} is value is taken less so that temperature value is overestimated considering worst case. That way the actual temperature and power loss will be less compared to the simulation version. The heat transfer coefficient for a 3-phase traction inverter and motor varies significantly depending on the cooling method (Ye, yang, Ge, P., & A., 2014). Table 3 presents the values of the C_{eq} and K_{heat} assumed for the simulation.

4.3 Simulation Results

Next the thermal dynamics models of the motor and inverter are integrated with the AVL VSM vehicle model. The vehicle parameters are that of Fiat E-Doblo provided by TOFAS. The high-fidelity simulation is run for the various simulation cases mentioned in simulation use cases under methodology section. The VSM/Simulink toolchain has the provision to choose between 4IWM and 2IWM drive. Also, the provision

to opt between rear wheel drive and front wheel drive. The power train choice for simulation work shown below is for a 2IWM rear wheel drive (RWD). At the end of the simulation run, the power loss and temperature profiles of the inverter and motor throughout the drive cycle can be observed.

4.3.1 Case 1: WLTC Drive Cycle

Figure 21 shows the simulation results of motor power loss and its temperature variation for WLTP drive cycle for a single motor of a 2IWM (RWD). An equal distribution of torque between the two motors is considered, since the WLTC does not contain lateral dynamics. The response and results of both the motors are therefore identical. Hence here results for single motor are used for the explanation purpose.

Figure 21 Simulation results showing power loss and its temperature variation on the WLTP drive cycle of Motor response for 2-IWM (RWD) drive at T_{amb} 20°C.

As seen from the temperature profile, the motor temperature gradually increases over time. The temperature of the component is directly connected to the power it dissipates, this can be seen from comparing the 2IWM and 4IWM power train topologies power losses/temperature profiles. For the same vehicle speed and torque request the motor torque demand is distributed among four motors for the 4IWM and two motors for the 2IWM configurations. Naturally, the power consumed by each of the 2IWM motors is higher than when considering four motors leading to higher power loss per motor as shown in Figure 22. As seen from the motor torque, a single motor draws more current to meet the higher torque

demand in 2IWM drive (Figure 21) as compared to the 4IWM drive (Figure 22). The HighScope project focuses on 2IWM drive system, the 4IWM drive is include for study and future explorative purposes.

Figure 22 Simulation results showing power loss and its temperature variation on the WLTP drive cycle of Motor response for 4IWM (AWD) drive at T_{amb} 20°C.

Similarly, Figure 23 and Figure 24 shows the inverter response showing the power loss and its temperature variation on the WLTP drive cycle at T_{amb} 20°C for a single inverter from 2IWM (RWD) and 4IWM (AWD) respectively. Here, it can be observed that the power loss and temperature are higher for a single inverter for a 2IWM drive compared to that of 4IWM drives. The value C_{eq} and K_{heat} for the inverter thermal dynamics are based on assumptions (on material and size) and requires temperature measured value for tuning these parameters as done for the IWM in Section 4.2. For this study the power loss of inverter was computed from the efficiency and input power provided by the BLW as shown in Figure 6. Implementing an updated surrogate model (measured power loss maps with temperature as an input function) and tuned parameters of the inverter thermal dynamics model, then the results are expected to vary. However, the qualitative trend or the pattern should remain the same.

Figure 23 Simulation results showing power loss and its temperature variation on the WLTP drive cycle of the traction inverter with 2IWM at T_{amb} 20°C.

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Figure 24 Simulation results of the traction inverter with 4IWM at T_{amb} 20°C on the WLTP drive cycle.

In the same set-up i.e. for WLTP drive cycle, simulation was carried out for different starting ambient temperature as shown in Figure 25. The temperature increases with the rise in the ambient temperature.

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(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Figure 25 Temperature variation for 2-IWM of motor and inverter at different ambient temperatures (a) -10°C (b) 0°C (c) 15°C (d) 20°C (d) 20°C (e) 30°C (f) 40°C.

Figure 26 shows the motor and inverter power loss for WLTP drive cycle simulated for two IWM (RWD). Here the power dissipation shown in the black dotted waveform is the amount of dissipation obtained by the thermal dynamic model for the motor winding. As seen from the figure the power loss increases with the increase in the ambient temperature.

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Figure 26 Various power loss variation for 2-IWM of motor and inverter at different ambient temperatures (a) -10°C (b) 0°C (c) 15°C (d) 20°C (e) 30°C (f) 40°C.

4.3.2 Case 2: Großglockner drive cycle showing the uphill case

This case studies the vehicle in an uphill scenario. Figure 27 shows the Großglockner drive cycle. The figure consists of five plots that describe different aspects of the vehicle's operation. The top plot shows the

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vehicle's speed over time. The average speed is shown as 63.22 km/h. The second plot shows the acceleration profile of the vehicle. The third plot represents the slope of the terrain as a percentage. A higher gradient corresponds to an uphill section, while a lower or negative gradient represents downhill driving. The terrain alternates between flat sections and slopes, suggesting diverse driving conditions. The fourth plot displays the power output of the vehicle over time. This power map will change based on the vehicle parameters. Peaks and troughs indicate periods of high energy demand (e.g., during acceleration or uphill driving) and energy recovery (e.g., during braking or downhill driving). The bottom plot shows the cumulative distance covered over time. The total distance driven is 13.12 km.

Figure 27 Großglockner drive cycle provide by WP5 partner AVL DE.

Next, this vehicle speed and gradient data of Großglockner drive cycle is added to the VSM/Simulink toolchain with the Fiat E-Doblo and the surrogate models of motor and inverter provided by ELAPHE and BLW. The thermal dynamics model will generate the temperature for this new drive cycle.

Figure 28 Simulation results showing power loss and its temperature variation on the Großglockner drive cycle of Motor response for 2-IWM (RWD) drive at $T_{amb} 30^{\circ}C$.

The Figure 28 shows the Fiat E-Doblo response to the Großglockner drive cycle. Due to the addition of road gradient (hill angle) additional tractive resistance force ($mg\sin\theta$) needs to be overcome by the vehicle as supposed to that on a plain road where this force is absent. Due to this hilly road becomes high torque demanding terrain and thus increasing the power consumption as shown in torque and power plots of Figure 28. The vehicle will operate in a high torque region inducing higher battery current and thus higher copper losses associated with the motor windings. This high power loss and high temperature response of the vehicle is seen in the simulation results.

Figure 29 shows the motor and inverter power loss for Großglockner drive cycle simulated for two IWM (RWD). The motor winding losses ($P_{loss,winding}$) contribute the most to the overall loss. A magnified view of a specific time window (384–390 seconds) is to highlight transient behaviours. It shows how losses in various components respond during a brief high-load or dynamic event.

Figure 29 Power loss variation for 2-IWM of motor and inverter at different ambient temperature T_{amb} 30°C.

4.3.3 Case 3: Heat up test for vehicle cabin

A simulation test has been performed to investigate the case of vehicle cabin heat scenario where the speed of the vehicle is kept constant. Figure 30 shows the simulation results. Here, the start temperature was set to -20°C, simulation duration was 30 minutes and vehicle speed was 50 km/h.

Figure 30 Simulation results showing the temperature and power loss profile of a single motor of a 2IWM drive (a) with efficient mode power loss maps and (b) inefficient mode power loss maps.

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Figure 30 (a) shows the power loss values from the efficient power loss maps and the Figure 30 (b) shows power loss values from an in-efficient power loss maps. The Figure 2 showed the efficient mode power loss maps used during normal traction mode. The in-efficient mode power loss map is different set of maps having higher power loss (drawing higher current) across all operating region of the motor which is only used for special condition like cabin heating.

Figure 31 Power loss variation for 2-IWM of motor and inverter at different ambient temperature $T_{amb} = -20^{\circ}\text{C}$ for a constant speed and torque operation.

The thermal dynamics model doesn't impose the cabin temperature, it only imposes the ambient (Coolant) temperature on the motor windings. Hence, as seen in the speed and torque plot of the Figure 30 is a constant value. That is for a constant vehicle speed the vehicle control unit will generate a constant torque at the steady state. The power loss maps of the motor will also produce the same power loss values for a set of motor torque and speed value.

The power loss profile for motor and inverter from both efficient and in-efficient power loss maps are shown in Figure 31. The output of the temperature dependent motor power loss maps remains constant for the whole simulation duration, thus the constant power loss value. The thermal dynamics model and temperature output is dependent on the power loss of the component. The heat transferred by the coolant is constant here.

From this case it is seen that for the purpose of vehicle heating the PE components must operate in in-efficient mode to generate any effective heat to be able to heat up the cabin. The motor is possible to operate in in-efficient mode if the torque demand is far from the motor's maximum torque at a given current speed. The motor can be operated in an inefficient way (i.e., increasing the current but without changing the torque, this is achieved by the field-weakening motor control).

5 Conclusion

Deliverable D2.4 represents a key milestone in validating the HighScape PE solutions' role in enhancing BEV performance across a comprehensive range of operational scenarios. Through a collaborative effort between USR and the other project partners the simulation-based framework developed provides actionable insights into the technical robustness and adaptability of the HighScape solutions under critical real-world conditions, such as extreme temperatures and demanding drive cycles. The iterative refinement process, supported by measurement data from component suppliers, ensures that the validation process remains dynamic and reflective of ongoing technological developments.

The simulation activity (thermal dynamics work) presented in Section 4 of this deliverable helps to emulate the power loss and temperature profile of the power electronics component when incorporated with the vehicle. These studies proved to be useful for the early-stage work development of the vehicle thermal management system of WP5. Simulation toolchain comes in handy and beneficial for such situation i.e. unavailability of components and bench test data.

5.1 Deviations, Impact and Recovery Actions

This deliverable is delayed by six weeks to perform the review for public release.

6 Bibliography

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